

‘Starflower’

**- an innovative
approach for
teaching outdoors in
physical education**

Introduction and direction

This edition of the starflower minipack, a 10-hour teaching plan, integrates outdoor learning with sustainable perspectives and provides an approach to teaching physical education within local nature or local environment with some nature qualities.

Teaching outdoors is often associated with the need for proper clothing and equipment. Our aim is to present an approach that makes outdoor education accessible to all students and teachers, regardless of equipment, gear, physical capabilities, and previous experience with outdoor activities.

This teaching plan addresses core aspects of planning, including student learning outcomes, a comprehensive structure of the course and implementation, and description of tasks (we call them loops) or outdoor learning activities aiming at students both developing practical outdoor skills and meeting ‘slow learning activities’ forefronting sensuous experiences and encounters with nature in the outdoors, with the aim of promoting environmental awareness and sustainability and connectedness to nature. The idea of ‘slow friluftsliv’, referred here as ‘slow outdoor life’ builds on the Nordic outdoor culture tradition named ‘friluftsliv’, and outdoor education in the tradition of friluftsliv as a remedy to create a bond with nature and an environmentally friendly way of life. The idea is supported by two relatively recent meta-analyses that confirm a connection between those who spend time in nature and a climate-positive behaviour ¹.

¹ Mackay, C. M., & Schmitt, M. T. (2019). Do people who feel connected to nature do more to protect it? A meta-analysis. *Journal of environmental psychology*, 65, 101323.

Whitburn, J., Linklater, W., & Abrahamse, W. (2020). Meta-analysis of human connection to nature and proenvironmental behavior. *Conservation biology*, 34(1), 180-193.

Student learning outcomes

- Become more familiar with the chosen natural surroundings, animals and plants, and how we humans are part of the great web of life.
- Know and can practice activities putting nature presence and nature experience in the fore and have a greater understanding of what nature presence and nature experience can mean for themselves and others.
- Dress appropriately and bring the necessary equipment to carry out simple outdoor activities in their own local environment.
- Use a compass to orient maps and follow a course off marked trails.
- Set up a gas storm kitchen and use it to boil water/tea and fry pancakes in a safe and practical way.
- Set up a simple but functional tarp using ropes and simple knots.

How to implement and facilitate the ten-hour Starflower teaching plan

Before we address important premises and guidelines on how to realise the Starflower teaching plan, we will share a short explanation of the Starflower methodology and how it is thought to be realized in this plan.

The illustration of the starflower methodology shows how students in groups and/or individually are invited to visit different loops and activities, whether practical skill-related or slow nature-based ones. The teacher is in the centre, at the campsite, and in the position to follow up and guide when needed. The four loops illustrated are all examples of interest for this teaching plan, and the more detailed instructions explaining the loops are presented later (attach 3). Note that the learning activities presented are developed and tested in Norwegian schools with a small nearby forest as the local teaching environment. The concept and the loops can be adjusted internationally to other school contexts and more or less natural surroundings. Probably would it be proper to change the “animals and life-forms” in the narratives,

and for example exchange the practical skill of putting up a tarp with another outdoor skill that fit the curriculum and local way of outdoor life.

The student groups will as a rule visit two loops each of the practical sessions, a practical-learning loop and a slow nature-based one. They meet one loop on the first "get-to-know-session". Furthermore, one of the practical loops demands a whole session. In total, there will be six loops during 4 sessions. The students themselves visit the different loops, read the instructions/invitations, and carry out as independently as they can. If they encounter challenges, they know where to find the teacher. The table below shows how this will work for one of the groups:

Session 1	Session 2	Session 3		Session 4	
Loop 1	Loop 2	Loop 3	Loop 4	Loop 5	Loop 6
Slow outdoor life: To be "at home" or belong in nature (2and2)	Practical: <i>Pancakes on a camp storm cooper</i> (group)	Practical: <i>Use compass to orient the map and follow a bearing</i> (group)	<i>Slow outdoor life: Let nature awaken your senses ...</i> (solitude)	Practical: <i>Setting up a tarp with rope and two simple knots</i> (group)	Slow outdoor life: <i>Nature is both strong and vulnerable</i>

Guideline 1: Tuning into the Starflower concept.

The students should be introduced to this period with outdoor activity well in advance. Partly to awaken (positive) expectations, but students should also feel that their own (potential) uncertainty and scepticism are being addressed. By this they will thus have an opportunity to prepare themselves.

Guideline 2: Overall plan covering a period of ten hours of teaching.

Session 1	Session 2, 3, 4	Session 5
Two hours	Each two hours	Two hours
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Walk to camp (with teacher) • Introduction – tuning in • Creating groups • Narrative • Become familiar with place through a “treasure hunt”. • Closure and return 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Walk to camp alone or in small groups. • Tuning in (narrative). • Starflower and carrying out loops in groups or alone. • Closure and return to school. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final reflections • Self-evaluation • Report?

We want students to learn the outdoors and we want them to develop awareness and connectedness to nature. In such a degree that they start thinking about nature's vulnerability and sustainability. To achieve this, we believe it is crucial to organise and teach these five sessions in a continuous period and manage to focus on continuity, recognition and depth throughout the period.

Guideline 3: Group cooperation and individual responsibility

The teaching plan emphasizes introduction of and practicing a selection of basic outdoor skills. It is expected that the students will arrive on time, dressed according to the conditions, and ready to cooperate with their fellow students. The plan is task-driven, the students are invited to interact in groups, and this requires the students to take responsibility for their own and others' learning. Highlighting what to expect from student can be both motivating and a way of bringing in some seriousness.

High goal achievement in this period can be summarized in the following four points:

- The student has participated constructively in group collaboration.
- The student has completed all subject loops with high effort.
- The student has engaged in conversations about outdoor life and sustainability.

- The student has submitted a report and self-assessment that describes what the student has completed, which of the goals the student masters, and which still require practice.

Guideline 4: Session One – setting the tone.

The first day (session) is about "reducing the news gap", building motivation, clarifying expectations, and making the starflower project a project everyone feels ownership of. The session consists of the following elements; minutes put in as a guideline:

Session 1	Time	Resp.
1. Collective walk from school to campsite.	10	Teacher
2. Gathering at camp (introduction, groups, letter from nature).	15	Teacher
3. Treasure hunt / rebus in groups.	20	Teacher
4. Starflower: Loop 1 - Slow outdoor life: Land art.	20	Teacher
5. Gathering - closure (Summary, reflections, "what's to come").	15	Teacher
6. Return to school and next class.	10	Students
	90	

On this first day, the class collectively walks to the campsite. It is a fine ambition that the students on following days meet directly at the campsite at the agreed time. This transition can be a challenge. Do we have the trust and calmness to let the students move alone and meet directly? Given that we only have two hours available, this will be an important way to "save" unnecessary time on relocation and organization, and we think that a short distance and use of the same natural area will help in this regard.

Premise: we think it is a basic competence in high school to meet at scheduled time, at the agreed place, prepared for what is to happen. It will be exciting to see how this type

of expectation is received by the students. Another premise is, of course, that the "local nature" is located at an acceptable distance from the school.

Gathered at the campsite, it is natural to talk about the program as a whole: purpose, organization in groups, type of loops, activities, and content, and what you as a teacher expect of the students. Regarding the purpose and goals of the program, one can relate to the curriculum directly, but perhaps more rewarding and tangible for the students if one ties it to the specific program and what you think the students will be left with afterwards. In the Norwegian context, it is (perhaps) natural to point out progression through several years, that this program builds important prerequisites that point towards expected end competence (cf. earlier about curriculum and objectives with the education).

A nice transition from "practical" conditions is to tell about "letters from nature". Teacher is by this challenged to share a narrative each session, starting from the first day. These letters are initially inspired by Norwegian circumstances, and you maybe/probably must create new narratives based on your local nature and wildlife.

The main idea of these narratives is to create a connection through the whole program regarding the main theme of nature awareness and sustainability. The sender of the

letters is a living creature (animals or plants) addressing the students/humans inviting them to think and feel - perhaps questions and wonderment are awakened.

As a teacher, you must prepare for this “presentation” and “performance” and think through how to follow up questions (the fox is addressing), but also link the deeper thoughts to the content and the program. In the letter we ore the fox has suggested some reflection questions. Hopefully, these letters (attached) will help set the tone for a vulnerable and more-than-human-centred nature.

After the gathering, two activities follow: "treasure hunt" and "land art". Both activities require the students to interact and will help to "set" the new group. Through the treasure hunt (attached), students become better acquainted with the area/place.

By introducing the “land art” loop on the first day, the teacher can explain the starflower methodology that students will explore in the coming weeks. It is no coincidence that a "slow nature-based" is chosen as a “beginner”. We believe it is important to emphasize this perspective so that it appears as natural as any other form of outdoor life. On this first day, all groups are assigned the same loop that the teacher reads aloud.

Guideline 5: How to do the main part: session two, three and four

In sessions two, three and four, students meet directly at the campsite. This gives the teacher the opportunity to prepare in advance. Here is a presentation and explanation of the program and structure for the three main sessions:

Organization and implementation of a two-hour session	Time	Resp.
1. Transition from school to campsite.	10	Students
2. Gathering at the campsite (circle, practicalities, narrative).	15	Teacher
3. Starflower methodology - the groups visit one/two loops each day.	40	Students
4. Gathering - closure (circle, sharing encounters, practical).	15	Teacher
5. Return to school and next class.	10	Students
	90	

Start (tuning in): The students meet at the campsite. The teacher invites them into a circle (around the campfire if possible). After practical messages, follows the sequence named: "Letter from nature" (see above).

The main part (starflower) is the different loops (tasks) that students receive/visit in groups organized according to starflower methodology. Descriptions of all the loops — practical and slow nature-based— are attached. The idea is that students themselves read, understand and carry out these loops. The teacher must be attentively present, guide as needed and otherwise be available for questions.

The end of the (closure) day takes place as a joint gathering. The students meet at the campsite, and find peace in the circle, and it is nice when the teacher picks up some reflections, some observations related to the theme that was set from the introduction, the narrative. Here one can also imagine that students have something to share from what they have experienced, related to nature or working on skill learning. Perhaps there is a need for practical clarifications, before heading back to school.

Guideline 6: Final session – closure

This last day/session is dedicated to reflection and assessment of what the students have been involved in and got out of it. How to do this is much up to the teacher, also reflecting the actual enactment of the starflower methodology. Teachers have organised for the students to deliver a report, some have used questionnaires, and other let the students share experiences in pairs as well as in a larger group in a circle. Consider if this last session should be conducted at the campsite or in another setting. It is important that students get to reflect upon, and maybe share, experiences, and emphasis should be placed on whether the encounter with nature, or what sometimes is called more-than-human world, has brought in some new perspectives. Furthermore, the reflection part should include thoughts on how the students think the starflower experiences relate to other learning activities in physical education. Here are some questions that the report or other forms of reflection should cover:

- What personal qualities are required to achieve and master outdoor life?
- In what way did you contribute positively to the collaboration in your group?
- Has this period of outdoor activity changed the way you think about nature?
- Which of the loops about slow outdoor life "spoke to you" - why?
- Which of the loops dealing with outdoor skills do you master / what do you need to practice more on?
- (Why) is "caring for nature" important?

Attachment 1: «Letter from nature»

DAY/SESSION ONE

Hello students. Welcome into nature. I hope you're sitting comfortably. You're probably wondering who I am? Maybe you'll guess it eventually. But thank you very much for the mission. What, haven't you heard about it... Exactly. But then it's about time!

I understand that this fall/spring you will visit this fantastic place in nature several times. Therefore, me and three of my friends in here have been asked if we can tell a little about life here inside and why it's important for us that you spend time here. Here is where we live and reside.

Today it's me you meet. And no, you won't know who I am yet. But maybe you'll understand it eventually.

I started by saying, "Welcome IN". Possibly, you usually say that you're going OUT on a trip. But have you thought about that here in the forest there are many who live, who spend all their time. I can tell you, we're doing well. But we have realized that it's important that we get to know the people who visit even better. And that the people get to know us even better. Have you thought about it, that you are visiting nature. Talk a little with the person sitting next to you - what do you think it means that you are visiting?

I'm a pretty little guy. I scurry around. In winter, I can dig a meter down into the ground to stay warm through the cold season. I watch out for the fox and the badger and others who prefer me as dinner. It usually goes well since I'm so small and fast. Plus, I hear incredibly well, in fact three times as good as you. I also have a very good sense of smell. Anyone figured out who I am?

It starts with M and ends with S. I'm a mouse, a forest mouse. Maybe you'll see me today, it's certain that I see and hear you. I won't disturb you. Maybe you can talk about what you really know about us forest mice.

I wish you a really nice day in the forest. Next time you'll get a greeting from a good friend of mine...

Questions for reflection:

- a) What does the forest mouse mean by: Welcome IN to nature?
- b) Do you think there are mice watching us now?
- c) What do you think they think of us?

DAY/SESSION TWO

Hello students. Here comes a new greeting from the forest. I'm supposed to greet you from my friend, the forest mouse. I'm not an animal. But I'm alive. I'm quite old. In fact, I can become as old as stone. Even though I don't scurry around like the forest mouse, I'm doing very well. I have a view and I have friends, many friends.

Many of them visit me regularly, some live inside me, on me and are completely dependent on me. You, humans, are also dependent on me. You know this, but let it sink in: I make oxygen and fresh air that you can breathe in... think about that... maybe on 1-2-3 you can take a good deep breath and inhale... delicious forest air? Have you put words to air before? Does it smell? Ask the person next to you what the air here tastes like?

Today, I want you to feel what it's like to be me. You must stand up. We start by closing our eyes. You must be completely quiet. But breathe in and out a few times. Breathe calmly and feel that your feet have a good grip on the ground. Pretend they are roots that keep you well planted on the ground. Feel how you can sway a little, but still have good control. Can you stretch out your arms? The arms are like branches that want to reach out to the sun as far as possible. There's a little wind, so they sway slowly from side to side. Gently from side to side.

Listen! What do you hear? What is the weakest sound you can hear that doesn't come from your friends in class. If you stretch out your hand, the teacher will put a little piece of me in your palm. You can taste me. It's not dangerous. In fact, I'm well suited for tea... Let the little needle move around in your mouth, feel how small and sharp I am. Try if you can chew... Can you taste it? It's the taste of me. Have you guessed who I am? Starts with S and ends with E. A very common tree in Norway, perhaps the most common.

Wish you a nice day in the forest. And feel free to contact - we can be friends!

Questions for reflection:

- a) What do you know about old trees - why are they important?
- b) Do you love trees? Do you have a favourite tree?
- c) Can trees be sad?

DAY/SESSION THREE

Hello students. Do you see that the teacher has taken off his shoes and socks today. That's strange. Yes, what was the first thing you thought when you saw a barefoot teacher...

Strange maybe. For you. Not for me. I go barefoot all the time. I must. I don't know how to make shoes, socks, or slippers. But I don't need it, I MUST feel the ground. It's vital. Then I can sneak up soundlessly. So quiet that no one notices me. But listen now because I'm going to tell you something strange. With your feet, you can move as quietly as me, in fact even more quietly.

I bet you haven't practiced that much. Besides, you might think it's strange, cold, wet, and even disgusting. But it's quite exciting too. During these days in the forest, I know you're going to be encouraged/challenged on exactly this. Watch out for shards of glass, I have to all the time. It's a complete disaster if I cut myself. You'll understand that - so I appreciate it if you help me by taking all the glass shards and tin cans you find in nature. I've heard that you call it leave no trace, a quite strange project, leave no trace. At least for us who are out here. You probably haven't thought that we who live out here in the forest are role models for what you call sustainable and leave no trace.

What, haven't I told you who I am? Have you guessed it? You'll get some hints. I'm very common in the forest. But it's rare you see me. I hunt at night. Sad to say, but the forest mouse is on my menu - that's how it is here in the forest. But that makes us live in the moment and appreciate every day, every sunrise, and the time we get. Who I am? I'm guessing some have guessed correctly now. Red--- 😊 And remember, your feet are also waterproof, and they benefit a lot from being aired and toughened a bit. Maybe you can talk a little about it - what you can learn from us animals in the forest... in addition to being traceless and sustainable.

Questions for reflection:

- a) When did you last go barefoot - how was it - is it a nature experience?
- b) Do you take trash with you when you find it in nature?
- c) Why don't we care so much about the animals in nature?

DAY/SESSION FOUR

Hello to you (in a deep voice). Welcome back to the forest. I am much larger than you think and I am actually right nearby. But even though I am huge, I am incredibly good at standing still. So still that everyone usually walks right past me. I also have horns, they fall off from time to time. Large horns. I've noticed that most people are bustling. They run off, hurry through nature. Rarely stand still like me. I wonder if they really manage to experience how nice it is, the harmony, the details, the atmosphere. Have you heard the phrase... forest tranquility! FOREST TRANQUILITY (even deeper).

Even though you hear city sounds, it is possible to use the other senses and discover some of the fantastic things happening here inside. But then you have to take it a little calmer, walk a little slower, maybe sit completely still for a few minutes (more than you've ever done before). Then you will notice small things, faint sounds, and colors. The smell of the forest, the smell of moss, the smell of autumn. Forest tranquility. Maybe you need to make several visits. But there is a tranquility here. Most things go slowly. Maybe you can describe the atmosphere you feel... while sitting quietly in the forest, just taking in the impressions. We who live here in the forest believe that you humans would really benefit from dwelling in this, just being with us around you. You can think about that... Meanwhile, I have to take a tour - after all, I am the king of the forest.

(Today the teacher will play a game in honor of me... but then you have to dare to be a little childish... he he, I'm standing right over there so I'm watching. HAVE A NICE DAY!)

Questions for reflection:

- a) Is the moose a role model for us humans?
- b) Is it important to take it a little easy - why is it good?
- c) Anyone want to share a nature experience of the type: a fantastic detail.

Attachment 2: “Treasure hunt”

The first day and first session are about getting to know the place and each other as a group. As a suggestion for how to build familiarity with the area, the teacher can hand out a map (see suggestion below) that covers the "100-meter forest", of the type "treasure map" or an orienteering map with a suitable scale.

Explanations:

- Campsite
- Pit
- Old pine
- Large stone
- “Jungle”
- End of plain
- By the stream

The teacher can present a piece of "land art" that indicates the four cardinal directions (north, south, west and east), and explain what it means to orient a map. Then: "Who can find the 'letters' and solve the 'puzzle'?" The map indicates stones, trees, and particular features in the area (plain, pit, stream, etc) where letters and numbers have been placed/hidden. As the students find letters, they get closer to the solution word. The purpose of the task is to make the students more familiar and comfortable with these surroundings. They are introduced to a very simple map and they also get to bodily experience the place and terrain.

"Treasure hunt" - hunting for letters that together form a solution word 😊							
1) W	2) I	3) L	4) D	5) L	6) I	7) F	8) E

Attachment 3: «Practical and slow nature-based loops»

Loop 1 - To be “at home” or belong in nature

In this loop, you as a group will cooperate to build/create a home, shelter, or hideaway for one or more of the creatures that live out here in nature.

It could be for a wood mouse or another animal that lives around here, but also for small, mysterious creatures that hardly anyone has seen. Feel free to use your imagination.

Walk around to see if you find a place that speaks to you: "Here! Here is someone who wants a house or shelter..." Then, just get started. You might want to spend a few minutes gathering suitable building materials (twigs, cones, stones, and branches).

You have 10-15 minutes for the task. Use your time well and remember not to harm nature.

When you are finished, you can take a picture of what you have created. Leave the home standing. Who knows, maybe someone will move in during the day.

We will meet at the gathering place.

(Teacher's consideration: Show the home to another group? Use picture in a report. Discuss if the structure should be dismantled in line with the principle of leaving no trace?)

Loop 2 - Pancakes on a camp storm cooker

Assigned equipment:

- 2 storm cookers with gas canisters
- Matches
- Frying spatulas
- Butter and jam (?)
- Pancake batter in a bottle

Nothing tastes as good as food made during a trip. It's great to set up a storm cooker, connect the gas, light it up, and then bake pancakes. This is what you will be practicing today.

Safety first! You must be careful when handling the storm cooker, gas, and matches. Therefore, a teacher will check that you have correctly set up the storm cooker and gas before you light it.

In the picture, you can see a correctly set up storm cooker.

Task

You are to collaborate in setting up two storm cookers and connecting the gas. Once you have lit the fire, each of you should cook a pancake.

Procedure

- Take out the parts of the storm cooker and notice how they are arranged initially.
- Assemble the storm cooker and prepare for cooking and boiling. (NB! A teacher should give the thumbs up)
- It's important that the camping stove is stable.
- It's also important that there is plenty of space so you don't knock the cooker over.
- Notice that there are "arms" for both the pan and the pots.
- Notice how you can adjust the temperature.
- Then you just have to cook nice golden pancakes and get used to using the tong. Good luck!

Final procedure

- Wait until the pan and camp storm cooker have cooled down before you pack them.
- Do you remember where the various parts should be placed/assembled?
- It's a good idea to "wash" or clean the pan with a little paper right away, it makes less work for you at home.

LOOP 3 - Use compass to orient the map and follow a bearing

Assigned equipment: - Digital compass (mobile phone)
- 2 manual compasses
- 2 maps

You've probably seen or used a compass before. You do know that you have a compass on your phone? It's exciting to go on a compass course, a form of treasure hunt or exploration. Today, you will practice basic compass use, both on your phone and with a manual compass. There are three tasks. If you master these three tasks, you have good control. You might wonder why it's good to know how to use a regular compass, what do you think? (answer at the bottom)

Task 1

You have a simple map of your area. But you see that there are marked lines on the map. These go SOUTH-NORTH. Can you orient the map using both compasses you have, both the digital and the manual one? Do they point in the same direction?

Task 2

Now you know where north is, right? Can you point it out? Does everyone in the group agree? The next you will do is to take a compass bearing. There is indeed a "treasure" at a bearing of ____ degrees. If you rotate the digital compass on your phone, you will see that it is possible to twist it until you get ____ degrees. Now the phone is pointing in the right direction. Follow this direction for _____ meters / steps.

Task 3

Do you remember the instructional video on how to use the compass and follow a compass bearing, with a regular compass? You're allowed to watch the video again... Can you figure out together how to take a bearing of _____ degrees and follow it for _____ meters / steps? New "treasure" 😊

question: The mobile phone can run out of battery, or it can rain, and then it's not so nice to use the mobile.

The teacher can give the students the task of watching a video like one of these before the lesson:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7MQUIYsmQhc> // <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rZd0RfsC-9I>

Loop 4 - Let nature awaken your senses...

1. Everyone in the group must take a sheet of paper.
2. Then, you each go in different directions, ALONE into the forest. Not far.
3. Find a spot and settle down comfortably on your sitting pad. Breathe and relax.

Perhaps you're leaning against a tree, or maybe you're lying in the moss. Are you comfortable?

Some people think that nature welcomes us. Many go into the wild to find peace and tranquility.

Now, some exercises are coming up to "awaken" your senses. I hope you'll give them a try.

Sight

Start by just looking around. What do you see? Do you see far away? Do you see close up? What do you notice? Do you see something you haven't seen before? Some say that humans mostly use their sense of sight. Is that the case for you? Here are some tasks that may make you more aware of your other senses...

Hearing

To listen, it might be a good idea to close your eyes. Just relax and breathe while you become aware of the sounds that surround you. Do you hear more than five sounds? Which one is furthest away? Which one is closest? Some people find it soothing to listen to nature, especially when the birds are singing. Can you relate to that?

Touch

Your body can feel, just like your hands. Have you felt how different things in nature feel? What does moss feel like? Is there something that is soft, hard, sharp, good, ...? It's nice to just lay heavily on the ground. Or lean against a tree. Some people like to hug trees.

Smell

What does nature smell like today? Can you describe that smell? Have you thought about what a pinecone smells like? What does the earth smell like? What does a tree smell like? Did you find a good smell? What does it do to you to smell a good scent in nature?

We're nearing the end. How was it? Would you say it was a nature experience? Is this something you can do again? A final challenge for the brave: do you dare to take off your shoes and socks, and walk barefoot back to the meeting place - how does that feel? Welcome back 😊

LOOP 5 - Setting up a tarp with rope and two simple knots

Assigned equipment: - Tarpaulin / tarp

- One solid rope and four less sturdy ropes

- Four pegs

When you go on a trip, it's very convenient to be able to create a "roof", whether it's to protect against sun or rain. As a group, you should practice setting up a simple tarp. Before setting up your own tarp, take a close look at a picture of a tarp or a tarp that the teacher has set up:

- Notice the tight tarp and tight ropes.
- The rope between the trees is tied with double half hitches at both ends. The guy lines, or ropes from each corner, are tied with slip knots in the tarpaulin and double half hitches in the peg. These knots are easy to untie. Other knots or knots made up on the spot can often be difficult to untie/loosen.
- The "roof" should not be too high (as it will allow rain in), but you should have ample space to sit under it.
- It is beneficial to set the pegs at an angle, not straight down into the ground.

Slip knot

Double half hitch

Task

You will now practice setting up a tarp. This should be done collaboratively. Take your time and make sure everyone is following along. Can you follow the procedure and meet all the details? This is a skill you will need later.

Procedure

- a) Fasten the sturdy rope between two trees at the height you desire. Do this several times so that everyone gets practice with the double half hitch knot. Are you satisfied with how tight you got the rope?
- b) Take the tarpaulin over the rope and use the four thin ropes in each corner. Here you should fasten with a slip knot at the corner of the tarpaulin and with a double half hitch in the peg. Tighten the tarp at the same time.
- c) Finished!

Loop 6 - Nature is both strong and vulnerable

Storms and earthquakes reveal nature as a powerful force. This strength is also evident in the small things, such as grass growing along the sidewalk edges or dandelions breaking through the asphalt.

At the same time, nature is fragile and vulnerable. If we pick a dandelion, it wilts and dies. If we cut down an old tree, planting a new one won't recreate the same atmosphere and life. Have you ever thought about how easy it is to destroy a spider's web?

The vulnerability of nature and life also relates to major challenges such as the climate crisis, pollution, and the way we humans are degrading nature and causing species extinction.

As a group, you are to find an example of something you believe can symbolize nature's strength and something that can symbolize nature's vulnerability.

Give yourself some time to walk around a little. First individually, then come together and discuss what you have seen. Once you have decided what you want to highlight, you should take two pictures:

- One picture that shows "nature's vulnerability."
- One picture that shows "nature's strength."

These pictures will later be included in your report. Feel free to take more pictures and try to capture both the strength and vulnerability of the natural element.